

TANGENT

WEBSITE AND SOCIAL NETWORKS PROFILES

D8.2

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Project Executive Summary

TANGENT is a project funded by the European Commission under the Research and Innovation Programme, which started in September 2021 and will end in August 2024. TANGENT is coordinated by the University of Deusto based in Bilbao, Spain. The pilot cities involved are Lisbon, Great Manchester, Rennes, and Athens.

The main objective of TANGENT is to develop new complementary tools for optimising traffic operations in a coordinated and dynamic way from a multimodal perspective and considering automated / non-automated vehicles, passengers, and freight transport. TANGENT allows the precise knowledge and management of the mobility flows among the transport modes and enables the implementation and integration of innovative mobility solutions, services, and business models.

The project contributes to more efficient traffic management, by reducing congestion, mitigate environmental effects through CO₂ reduction, increasing safety and economic advantage. TANGENT helps the pilot cities to achieve a 10% reduction travel time, 8-10% reduction in CO₂ emissions, 5% reduction of accidents, 10-15% increase in use of public transport.

TANGENT partners

The partnership is composed by 13 partners, including universities, research laboratories and innovation hubs, consultancies, city authorities, a software provider, a public transport company and a network organization. The partners come from eight EU Member States and one non-EU Member State: Belgium, France, Germany, Greece, Italy, Netherlands, Portugal, Spain, United Kingdom.

- University of Deusto
- Aimsun
- National Technical University of Athens
- Interuniversity Microelectronics Centre
- Cefriel
- Rupprecht Consult
- ID4CAR
- The City of Rennes
- A-to-Be – Mobility Technology
- Carris
- Transport for Greater Manchester
- Panteia
- POLIS

https://twitter.com/TANGENT_H2020

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/tangent-project/>

https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCjhz4kwEm_sTHj7fE4zXToA

For further information please visit <http://www.tangent-h2020.eu/>

Deliverable executive summary

This deliverable gives proof and details of TANGENT website and social media accounts that will provide information on the evolution of the project to a wide audience. It provides detailed information about the overall structure, layout, and main features of the project website, which will be the most relevant interface to the public and useful to showcase all related information and disseminate the future results achieved.

In addition, three social media channels will be used throughout the project duration: Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube. They are particularly used by any type of professional and they are a widespread tool to share, promote and access information via short, direct, and targeted messages. The document provides information about the accounts, explaining why they are going to be used and providing an overview of the chosen layout (logo and banners).

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
WP	Work Package

1 Purpose of the deliverable

1.1 Attainment of the objectives and explanation of deviations

The objectives related to this deliverable have been fully achieved.

The social media accounts – Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube – have been activated November 2021.

The concept, structure and layout of the project website has been prepared by the selected web designer identified by POLIS through a specific tender. The contents and structure of the website has been then agreed with the project coordinator in November 2021.

The website goes live in the first half of January 2022.

1.2 Intended audience

The website and social media accounts are created to reach the largest audience possible, both composed by transport professionals, policy makers, technical experts, and single individuals not necessarily involved in the transport and urban planning domains. The list of potential audience is very large and composed by:

- Transport operators and public authorities with competency in transport matters:
 - City and regional administrations
 - National authorities
 - EU Institutions
- Technology providers of solutions for transport management which commercialise solutions like TANGENT. They could benefit from collaboration agreements, technology transfer, etc.
- Policy makers: They can benefit from the recommendations delivered in TANGENT in a final event to support them in their decision-making process.
- Academics and students: dissemination will evidence the potential of TANGENT research to be applied in other projects and domains.
- European citizens and society in general, as final beneficiaries and center of the progress done in traffic and mobility management.
- EU-wide transport networks.

2 Website and social media accounts

2.1 Website

Today, websites are the first address of information for any topic. Thus, the TANGENT website aims to provide comprehensive overview on the project, including the aims, outcomes, and methodology of the TANGENT project. It is the project's first representation for external stakeholders, providing key information about the project.

Visitors will be able to quickly find basic information on the project, such as methodology, demonstration areas, results, partners, publications, news, and success stories partners. The updating process of the website is designed to be user friendly and does not require specialised skills and the content management system allows for the easy creation of new pages, inclusion of new text and image content.

The website also includes links to the social media channels, i.e., Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube.

The website will be kept up to date with the latest news, events, and project developments. As stated in the Grant Agreement (GA) the Work Package (WP) Leader, POLIS, will lead the updating process, and liaise with the other consortium members for relevant activities and projects. The TANGENT website will be made available throughout the entire duration of the project and beyond, for a period yet to be defined. All project public results will be included.

The TANGENT website domain name is: www.tangent-h2020.eu

After a review of the project coordinator, the website goes live in the first half of January 2022.

The following briefly presents the layout of the website, its structure, and main features.

2.1.1 Structure

The TANGENT website is clearly structured to present the objective and method of the project and allow the readers to understand the structure. Its categories are the following ones:

- Home
- About TANGENT
- Partners
- Cities
- Resources
- News & Events
- Contact

General information on the project can be found under the first tab "About TANGENT". This links to the sections "What is TANGENT", "Context", "Concept and Methodology", "Objectives" and "Work Packages".

The section "Partners" gives visibility to all 13 project partners, including their logo, contacts, hyperlinks to their respective websites and a short profile description.

The section "Cities" provides overall information about the four case studies: Lisbon, Great Manchester, Rennes, Athens.

The “Resources” section will list the project deliverables and other useful materials, such as Newsletters or promotional materials.

The “News & Events” section will offer news from the project and its partners.

The “Contact” page allows anyone to reach out the project coordinator for any type of request.

The sitemap is represented in detail by the following table.

About TANGENT	Partners	Cities	Resources	News and Events	Contact
What is TANGENT	Full list	Lisbon	Deliverables		
Context		Great Manchester	Newsletters		
Concept and Methodology		Rennes	Promotion materials		
Objectives		Athens			
Work Packages					
Facts					

Table 1 Website structure

2.1.2 Homepage

The TANGENT website homepage has the following structure:

- Menu linking to the website’s respective pages
- Links to social media: LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube
- A paragraph presenting the TANGENT mission and a link towards more information
- Latest news and events
- Possibility to subscribe to the newsletter
- The EU flag and the following text: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 955273” appears on all the pages of the website.

Figure 1 - Website - Homepage

Figure 2: Website - Newsletter subscription feature

2.1.3 About the project

TANGENT targets a variety of stakeholders that might not be familiar with EU projects and their structure. Therefore, the about section outlines the structure of the project in an understandable and easy language. The section introduces the TANGENT project, its missions, objectives, and partners. It will further link to other projects were appropriate.

This section will also explain how the public can cooperate with the projects, through formalised structures such as the exchange forum, as well as other cooperation options and agreements.

Figure 3: Website - About the project

2.1.4 Cities

TANGENT approach and methodology will be tested in three case studies: Rennes (France), Lisbon (Portugal), Great Manchester (United Kingdom) and a virtual case study in Athens (Greece) with real data from various modes of transport, under different traffic events such as bottlenecks, accidents, pedestrian flows etc.

Figure 4: Website - Cities

2.1.5 Partners

The partnership is composed by 13 partners, including universities, research laboratories and innovation hubs, consultancies, city authorities, a software provider, a public transport company and a network organisation.

The partners come from eight EU Member States and one non-EU Member State: Belgium, France, Germany, Greece, Italy, Netherlands, Portugal, Spain, United Kingdom.

Figure 5: Website - Partners

2.1.6 Resources

The project results will be published mainly in this section, in the form of deliverables, newsletters, and promotional materials.

Figure 6: Website - Resources

2.1.7 News and Events

The News and Events section is regularly updated with news of the project but will occasionally also feature news about external developments that are relevant for the project. It features news about workshops and events the project conducts but also articles on new TANGENT publications.

2.1.8 Contact

The contact form allows people to contact the project coordinator or communication manager easily for any kind of request related to the project.

Figure 7: Website - Contact

2.2 Social media

Social media will play a relevant role to reach the overall project communication objectives. By using social and digital media, the project aims to fulfil the following objectives:

- Steering additional traffic to the TANGENT website.
- Complementing traditional communications channels e.g. printed publications, events, press outreach and targeted mailings.
- Give an informal voice to TANGENT.
- Monitoring mentions of the TANGENT project, project partners, project outcomes and other important activities.
- Providing on-site and live coverage of key events for those who cannot attend.

2.2.1 Twitter

The TANGENT Twitter page can be accessed at: https://twitter.com/TANGENT_H2020, with the following Twitter handle: @TANGENT_H2020.

Tweets will include:

- The latest news from the project
- News and pictures from meetings or workshops
- News and pictures from local use cases
- News on topics related to urban mobility, city logistics, innovative urban planning concepts and tools, planning for multimodal transport
- Retweets from related twitter accounts of initiatives, partners, cities, and projects

The TANGENT Twitter account and website refer to each other. The latest tweets are visible on the website via a Twitter feed.

The following hashtags have been preliminarily identified to enhance the reach of the messages sent via Twitter: #TANGENTproject, #TANGENT_h2020, #trafficmanagement, #multimodaltransport, #transportmodelling #greentransport

The list will be further refined and updated in the upcoming months, targeted also on the results and deliverables of the project.

Interaction with EU official accounts is expected, especially on transport and mobility related contents.

Below a screenshot of the Twitter page:

Figure 8: Twitter

Role of partners:

Polis manages the TANGENT Twitter account.

All partners provide news and images for Twitter when appropriate.

All partners tweet from events and retweet TANGENT when possible.

2.2.2 LinkedIn

The TANGENT LinkedIn page can be accessed at: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/77112920/>
The aim of the page is to:

- Enable knowledge transfer between local authorities and other urban transport stakeholders
- Share experiences and enhance collaboration
- Keep in touch with peers
- Keep up to date with advancements in the project
- Announce events

The following hashtags have been preliminarily identified to enhance the reach of the messages sent via LinkedIn: #TANGENTproject, #TANGENT_h2020, #trafficmanagement, #multimodaltransport, #transportmodelling #greentransport

The list will be further refined and updated in the upcoming months, targeted also on the results and deliverables of the project.

Interaction with EU official accounts is expected, especially on transport and mobility related contents.

Below a screenshot of the LinkedIn page:

Figure 9: LinkedIn

Role of partners:

Polis manages the TANGENT LinkedIn account.

All partners provide news and images for LinkedIn when appropriate.

All partners are invited to share, like or comment TANGENT posts when possible.

2.2.3 YouTube

The TANGENT YouTube page can be accessed at:

https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCjhz4kwEm_sTHj7fE4zXTToA

The aim of the TANGENT YouTube account is to publish and disseminate the following videos:

- One promotional video of the project
- Additional videos – exact number to be determined - focusing on the pilot activities carried out in the demonstration areas

The contents will be further refined in the upcoming months, targeted also on the results achieved by the cities involved.

Below a screenshot of the YouTube page:

Role of partners:

Polis manages the TANGENT YouTube account.

All partners are invited to share, like or comment TANGENT posts when possible.

Figure 10: YouTube